

BASICS OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article describes the main provisions of the investment activity in Uzbekistan, the types of investments for the purposes of their fulfillment, sources of financing. There is presented the most important results of the implementation of investment projects in 2015, as well the main objectives of the investment in the current year in the country.

Keywords: investments, investor, investment, property, project, investment entities, investment funds, capital investments, innovative investment, social investment.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the role of innovation-filled investments is significantly increasing. It is they who contribute to the modernization of the real sector of the country's economy and the creation of a new quality foundation for sustainable, progressive economic development. In accordance with the theory of competition M. The competitive positions of the national economy provide advantages in production factors, as well as investments and innovations Over the years of the formation of a socially oriented market economy in Uzbekistan, the focus of scientists and practitioners has constantly been on the creation of favorable legal, organizational and economic conditions for attracting investment in various sectors of the national economy. A package of legislative acts regulating relations in the field of investment activity was adopted. Thus, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investment Activity" reveals the basic concepts in the field of investment activity. In particular, the following important definitions are given: – investments — tangible and intangible benefits and rights to them, including intellectual property rights, as well as reinvestments invested in objects of entrepreneurial and other types of activities not prohibited by law;

– investor — a subject of investment activity that invests its own funds and attracts other investment resources into objects of investment activity; – investment activity — a set of actions of subjects of investment activity related to the implementation of investments. These definitions clearly delineate the legal field of activity for entrepreneurs, business entities, government agencies and non-governmental organizations, creating opportunities for delineating rights and obligations in the implementation of investment activities. Based on the above definitions, a legal framework has been created in Uzbekistan for serious attention to each type of investment. First of all, these are capital investments, which include investments invested in the creation and reproduction of fixed assets, including new construction, modernization, reconstruction, technical re–equipment, as well as in the development of other forms of material production. Innovative investments in the republic include investments invested in the development and development of new or improved goods (works, services), the production process, a new marketing method or organizational method in conducting business. An important place is occupied by social investments. These are investments invested in the development of human potential, skills and industrial experience, as well as in the development of other forms of intangible benefits.

In order to ensure the further introduction of progressive methods of organizing design work based on international best practices, modern construction standards and accelerate the transition to market methods of determining the cost of construction, as well as improving the efficiency of the use of funds in the implementation of investment projects financed by centralized investments, a Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve design works and expertise of investment projects, financed by centralized investments"¹. It approved Comprehensive measures to reduce and

optimize the structure of costs in the implementation of design and survey and construction works of facilities financed by centralized investments. In general, capital investments in the country's economy contribute to the achievement of sustainable and dynamic development of knowledge-intensive industries, competitive, high-tech and environmentally friendly industries. Significant resources are allocated to the development of the social sphere, the implementation of a training program, the improvement of the health care system, and the provision of high-quality public services to the population. At the same time, there are still unrealized opportunities and reserves in the comprehensive work on the formation of a favorable investment climate in Uzbekistan. Thus, a leading researcher at the Institute of Forecasting and Macroeconomic Research under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (IPMI), Ph.D. in Economics. G. Fedyasheva, analyzing the growth of fixed capital accumulation in the economy of Uzbekistan, writes that in general, despite the difficult post-crisis conditions of development, the country was able not only to preserve, but also to increase public wealth in the form of fixed capital accumulation. But in order to match the developed countries in terms of accumulated capital and technological level of production, it should have approximately equal to them Resolution No. 15 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 22, 2016 "On additional measures to improve design work and expertise of investment projects financed by centralized investments". // Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2016, No. 4, Article 35. the amount of accumulated capital per capita 2. Today there are quite a few well-founded points of view among domestic scientists and experts on solving the problem of improving the efficiency of investment activity. They propose various measures that contribute to the optimization of the algorithm for organizing all investment activities, qualitative improvement of management in this

area, ways to increase the effectiveness of regional investment programs, support for exporting enterprises, and improve the activities of banks.

Scientists of Uzbekistan: Doctor of Economics S. Chepel and Candidate of Economics N. Abdunazarova, one of the priority areas for improving the functions of state management of the economy determine the gradual restriction of investment flows distributed within the investment program only to large strategic projects that have a high multiplier effect for the entire economy and resource conservation with a simultaneous increase in the share of non-state investments distributed on market conditions. Of particular interest is the regional aspect of the problem of investment in the economy. In this regard, a senior researcher at IPMI, Candidate of Economics, Rafiev A. notes that regional investment projects are being actively implemented taking into account the natural economic potential, socio-demographic characteristics of the regions of the republic, as well as the necessary institutional measures to improve the investment climate of the region. At the same time, a single integrated approach to the formation of regional investment programs and management systems has not been developed, their implementation is not monitored in order to prepare comprehensive regional investment programs, they are offered the following sequence of their formation:

- strategic analysis of investment activity development;
- development of strategic directions of investment activity based on definitions of promising investment projects;
- development of a strategy for the formation of investment resources;
- development of program measures to create a favorable environment for attracting investment in the region's economy;
- evaluation of the developed investment strategy. According to a senior lecturer at the University of Westminster in Tashkent, Makhmudov M. – critically

assessing the effectiveness of the current mechanism for financing programs to increase the export potential of key exporting enterprises, it should be recognized that the range and scale of work carried out in this direction lags far behind the real needs of the national economy. Taking into account the exhaustion and limitations of the sources of financing used, it is important to introduce into the economic practice of the republic such promising methods of investment support for key enterprises as syndicated lending and bank project financing, venture, equity and grant financing, leasing, franchising, public-private partnership, etc.

One of the most important factors in increasing the efficiency of investments in the economy of Uzbekistan is, of course, the stable functioning of the country's banking system. Associate Professor of the Branch of Plekhanov Russian University of Economics in Tashkent, Candidate of Economics Abdullayeva Sh. He notes that despite the results achieved in ensuring the financial stability of the banking system and increasing the role of commercial banks in the development of the national economy, there are a number of problems that need to be solved. For example, the share of banks remains low not only in financing investments in fixed assets, in general, the share of assets of commercial banks in the GDP structure is 37%, capital is 5.5%, which indicates the presence of unrealized growth potential of credit and investment operations of commercial banks.

From the author's point of view, in order to increase the role of commercial banks in investment support of innovative development of the national economy, it is possible to consider the following areas:

- improvement of the regulatory framework and creation of additional fiscal incentives for more active participation of banks at the stage of project development, as well as the creation of banking syndicates to finance large innovative projects;

- attracting foreign investment funds, international economic and financial institutions to create joint investment companies with commercial banks to finance the start-up capital for the implementation of innovative projects, with the possible next sale of the financial institution's stake to the main founders. Analyzing the problems of organizing long-term funding of the banking system of Uzbekistan and ways to solve them, senior lecturer of TSEU Kharchenko L. He believes that the shortage of "long-term investments", which are formed in the economy through several channels: bank lending, government spending, the capital market, leads to the fact that the economy, sooner or later, faces the need to develop a local market for long-term debt obligations. Most Uzbek banks are "funded" at the expense of clients whose resources, by their nature, are "short-term", that is, "on demand" (more than 50% of all balances on client accounts). The most popular source of long-term resources of domestic banks is deposits of the population. Funds of legal entities, as resources, "break up" into two components: the first is the balances on the settlement and current accounts of domestic enterprises, the growth of which, in the long term, is not expected; the second part is "term deposits" of this category of depositors, the proportion of which is significantly lower. It becomes obvious, L. Kharchenko notes, that the "traditional way" of long-term lending at the expense of deposits does not justify itself either from the point of view of "bank liquidity" and "bank risks", nor from the point of view of "efficiency" of capital use, and the search for sources of long-term funding needs to be accelerated.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Paying attention to the long-term housing savings of citizens, the author believes that at the current level of development of domestic finance, only the banking system is able to provide for such a large number of customers a reliable accumulation and preservation of primary mortgage contributions. A special and

important case of targeted savings is pension savings. Another promising direction in the field of "long-term funding" is the securitization of portfolios of homogeneous loans not only in mortgages, but also in other instruments (credit cards, consumer loans, loans to small businesses and private entrepreneurship). Securitization is currently a little-studied element for the domestic financial market. However, it requires effective implementation and use of infrastructure conditions and large-scale efforts, primarily on the part of the state¹. These points of view indicate that Uzbekistan's experts are constantly monitoring the processes of attracting new investment resources to the economy. Noting the convincing positive results achieved in the field of investment, they also highlight unrealized opportunities to increase the efficiency of investment activities in various sectors of the economy. In our opinion, scientific analysis, formulation of recommendations on improving the mechanism for attracting investments into the economy of Uzbekistan, are not only of serious scientific interest, but also have important practical significance. This concerns both the identification of sources of financing for various projects and the choice of tools for their implementation. The adopted document approved the main parameters of capital investments and the forecast for the commissioning of social facilities, as well as the targeted program for the commissioning of facilities and production facilities. Considering the above, the following main conclusions can be formulated:

1. Comprehensive measures taken in Uzbekistan have made it possible to ensure sufficiently high rates of investment growth in various sectors of the national economy.
2. There is a tendency to decrease the share of centralized investments and increase the role of market sources of financing.

3. It seems expedient to improve investment activity in the republic in the coming years, taking into account: – priority financing of industrial construction; – expansion of investment activity of banks; – implementation of deep structural transformations in the economy; – features and prospects of socio-economic development of regions; – ongoing global crisis, uncertainty and increased competition in world markets.

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